

Publishing Research Data

[Alongside publishing your research findings](#), it is considered good practice – and often a requirement – to make the data that support your findings available to the research community. This promotes reproducibility of your findings and enables the reuse of your data in future research.

Before sharing your data, ensure you are allowed to! Beware of legal and ethical restrictions, especially for personal or other sensitive data. To publish your data, follow the FAIR principles and use a suitable repository that allows you to add proper documentation and metadata.

When selecting a repository, check the requirements of your research funding organization. Many require data publication in accordance with FAIR principles and the use of non-commercial repositories.

Recommended repositories

Subject-specific repositories:

- [DaSCH](#) – Swiss National Data and Service Centre for the Humanities
- [SWISSUbase](#), especially for social sciences and linguistics

Interdisciplinary repositories:

- [Zenodo](#) is a research data repository created, hosted and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE.
- [Dryad](#) is a research data repository, originally funded by the National Science Foundation U.S., governed by a nonprofit membership organization.

Institutional repositories:

The University of Basel does not provide an institutional repository and recommends using existing subject-specific or general repositories. If collaborating with other universities, you might have the option to publish data through their repositories.

Repository registries:

- The [Swiss National Science Foundation \(SNSF\)](#) provides a list of generalist, discipline-specific and institutional data repositories.
- The [Open Access Directory](#) provides a list of repositories for open data of various disciplines.
- [Deposition Databases](#) by Elixir, provides a list of repositories for biomolecular data.
- Find more repositories via [re3data](#): a registry of research data repositories.

